

SHERPA
Rural Science-Society-Policy
Interfaces

MAP Position Paper

ALTERNATIVE RURAL FUTURES (FORESIGHT)

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1. Key messages

This second phase of the SHERPA MAP work made it possible to refine the forward-looking reflections developed in 2020. It was based on the JRC's scenarios on rural areas by 2040 built on two axes: demography and governance. At the end of the first workshop organised in July 2021, **a majority of participants positioned the Provence Alpes Côte d'Azur region in scenario 1 ("Rurbanities"), with a growing rural population and fragmented multi-level governance in the regions. rural areas.** However, participants also cited Scenarios 2 (Rural renewal) and 3 (Rural connections). In general, it is difficult to position the entire region on one of the four scenarios due to the strong subregional heterogeneity of rural territories. **By 2040, the members of the platform have converged to place the future of the rural areas of the Provence Alpes Côte d'Azur region in a scenario of rural renewal.**

During the second workshop in September, 8 priorities were identified to achieve this desirable future in rural areas: **access to housing, mobility, access to local services, access to digital technology, adaptation to change climate, the economy and employment, the development and the adaptation of the agricultural and food sector and finally the tourism sector.** For each of these priorities, two objectives have been identified, as well as avenues for transitional measures, tools to be mobilised, the actors concerned, and constraints to be overcome.

To implement all these measures and respond in a sustainable manner to the challenges of rural territories in the Provence Alpes Côte d'Azur region, the issue of governance of resilience to pilot transitions was the subject of a third workshop which aimed to answer four questions:

- What relevant scales of governance, what coordination is needed?
- What engineering, territorial contractualisation and animation are required?
- What policy instruments, funding, monitoring and evaluation tools should be used?
- How can citizens be involved more and more effectively?

It emerges that an approach as close as possible to the territories (at the level of a living area) is essential and that the different decision levels must be better known and better coordinated. Administrative and financial procedures, in particular concerning European projects, including within the framework of the ERDF and the EAFRD, must be simplified, and the financing tools be better suited to the needs and capacities of project promoters, including in terms of pre-financing. To promote the emergence of these projects and allow their implementation and monitoring, it is essential to provide and pool support in terms of territorial engineering, intended for municipalities and institutionalised groups of municipalities¹, etc., but also for other local actors (associative structures, citizen groups, development agencies, etc.).

Finally, for sustainable policies, the involvement of users and citizens must be rethought to move from consultation to co-construction.

Keywords: agriculture, climate change, natural capital, demography, rural economy, local economy, employment, governance, mobility, digital development, management of natural resources, quality of life, rurality, sedentary lifestyle, access to services, rural areas, tourism

¹ In French : Etablissement Public de Coopération Intercommunale or Pôle d'Equilibre Territorial Rural.

2. Positioning the region in future rural areas foresight

1.1. What desirable future for the rural areas of the Provence Alpes Côte d'Azur region?

At the end of the first workshop, a majority of participants positioned **the Provence Alpes Côte d'Azur region in scenario 1 of the JRC on rural areas by 2040 ("Rurbanities"), with a growing rural population and fragmented multi-level governance in rural areas**. However, participants also referred to scenarios 2 (Rural renewal) and 3 (Rural connections). In general, it is difficult to position the entire region on one of the four scenarios due to the very subregional heterogeneity of rural territories. This results in the need for a very detailed territorial approach at the level of the living areas, and groups of municipalities to better understand the issues specific to each rural territory.

The exchanges between the members of the platform during the first workshop in July converged to **include the future of the region's rural territories in respect of the scenario of rural renewal, the contours of which are specified below**.

1.1.1. DEMOGRAPHY

According to INSEE projections, population growth should continue in rural areas, but at a slower pace and will be mainly driven by the migration that the health crisis has reinforced. However, today people are more mobile and therefore the migratory factor is very volatile.

The aging of the population is certain, it will become more pronounced with the arrival of generations of baby boomers. At the same time, the youth deficit will increase substantially by 2030, particularly in rural areas, accentuating the reduction in the working-age population. As a result, there is a risk that the dependency ratio will deteriorate further if no action is taken.

The challenge is therefore to support this trend of settling in rural areas, accentuated by the COVID crisis. In particular, it is a question of attracting young populations in particular by making these areas attractive and by providing access to services adapted to the expectations of these populations: housing, education, household services, child care services, cultural offer. This contributes to create an enabling environment to job creation, in particular via networks of dynamic actors, support for young project leaders and through digital development. In addition, the installation of these new populations in rural territories requires collective actions aimed at resolving conflicts of resource use and promoting good living together.

Finally, the Provence Alpes Côte d'Azur region must promote the development of numerous personal assistance services in these areas (training, upgrading of these jobs, etc.), to respond to the care of the elderly, whose number is increasing strongly.

1.1.2. LIFE FRAMEWORK AND QUALITY LIFE

To strengthen the attractiveness of rural areas, in addition to preserving natural capital and improving access to services across all areas, initiatives should be developed on the basis of the cultural and social capital of rural areas to enhance the quality of life. It is about reinventing a belonging to the territories and a positive rurality. Locally, support for the creation of meeting places, and enhancing conviviality more generally, should be implemented with appropriate financial tools (see governance point), in order to promote "good living" between generations and between long-term residents, new residents, new arrivals and tourists, helping to alleviate conflicts. These places of life can be hybrid with a commercial vocation, but also socially grounded, and provide public services (cafés, country bistros, AMAP, solidarity grocery stores, homes, etc.). Cultural and social actions aimed at strengthening citizen participation in the life of communities in solidarity should also be promoted.

1.1.3. TRANSITION NECESSARY TO TAKE CLIMATE CHANGE INTO ACCOUNT

The effects of climate change will become more pronounced by 2040 and will have a lasting impact on biodiversity, forests and water resources. It is in this context that the region must put in place its Climate Plan, through a COP, which aims in particular to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, in particular through an overhaul of the territorial organisation of transport, the development of soft transport, the development of access to remote (digital) services, adaptations in agricultural production methods, but also the increase in the production of renewable energies in rural areas and better protection of the habitat.

The Climate Plan also provides for the preservation of biodiversity and natural resources, which contributes to combating the effects of climate change and natural disasters (fires, floods, landslides) with the strengthening of protected areas including parks. In this context, mitigation policies must be developed and implemented in each territory, relying in particular on the work of the Regional Group of Experts on the Climate (GREC-South) and on the regional natural parks, which are mainly responsible for preserving biodiversity and natural areas.

The Climate Plan also provides for promotion of the control of water resources and the preservation of aquatic environments. Overall, in each of the rural territories, it is a question of implementing more resilient and more sustainable development models, creating innovations and new jobs for better preservation and management of territories and natural resources (water, forests, biodiversity), but also responding to the specific challenges of the tourism sector and the agricultural sector.

1.1.4. ECONOMY AND EMPLOYMENT IN RURAL AREAS

Given the importance of the local economy (shops, crafts, small businesses, personal services, cultural services, etc.) for the life of rural areas, supporting this economy is a major issue. It is a source of jobs and activity. It is in direct contact with the territory by promoting local heritage and know-how, using local material and human resources. Finally, this local economy has a strong social utility: it provides many essential services and offers places of conviviality and exchanges, generating links between generations and/or populations. To promote its development, appropriate financing tools will have to be developed that considers the social utility of this generally poorly or unpaid economy. By 2040, personal services must be developed and enhanced to respond to the aging of the population. Likewise, the offer of services adapted to new, younger residents should be developed (early childhood, cultural services, etc.).

Sustainable territorialised agricultural and food systems must be put in place that respond to multiple challenges: the renewal of generations; the dependence on imported labour which weakened the sector during the health crisis and raised the question of the social management of agricultural labour; the sharp drop in the number of farms due to retirements not replaced and land pressure linked to the artificialisation of land; taking into account strong natural constraints and adaptation to climate change (management of climate risk, access to irrigation water, adaptation of crops); multi-activity and diversification of production, economic viability and resilience to production crises. The short circuits that the health crisis has helped bring to the organisation of the sectors and regional food projects must prompt the development of local agriculture, better pay for farmers, and limit dependence on imported food products.

New tourism models specific to each territory must be developed, offering tourism that responds to the effects of climate change (in the mountains, but also on the coast and in the "middle country"); the decline in foreign tourism which could continue; new forms of tourism (elderly people, family tourism, cultural tourism, local tourism, etc.) and the demands of tourists in terms of environmental preservation and sustainable development. This offer must favour the sustainable development of a unique natural, historical and cultural heritage.

The development of the green economy and the circular economy (agroecological transition, waste management, renewable energy production and insulation of housing), but also of the social and solidarity

economy, already strongly established in rural areas, is also a priority. They are important sources of new business and jobs.

The digital development programmed throughout the region can be a tremendous asset for activity in rural areas. It is a source of competitiveness and innovation and promotes employment through the development of remote work and the emergence of new forms of collaborative work.

The special status of seasonal workers and multi-active workers must be strengthened and be more protective, helping to improve the attractiveness of rural areas and the treatment of workers. This status requires a special scheme within the framework of the unemployment insurance reform project.

To support these transitions, create the activities and jobs of tomorrow, a training offer adapted to the different job opportunities must be developed for job pools, which will be developed and updated with all the actors concerned, on the basis of the territorial diagnosis.

1.1.5. LAND USES AND THE ENVIRONMENT

The preservation and restoration of ecological continuities is an essential issue for the maintenance of regional biodiversity. Stopping the artificialisation of natural territories and agricultural land is included in all land-use planning documents, which must be implemented and controlled. The establishment and transfer of agricultural land must be encouraged in order to attract new farmers (land bank, pre-emption, support to setting-up news farmers, etc.).

By 2040, the aim will be to significantly strengthen European and national support, intended in particular for agricultural production that is more respectful of the environment, such as organic farming and agri-environmental measures (Pillar 2 of the CAP), as well as to food quality chains.

The territorial natural heritage must be considered as a common good and its ecosystem services necessary for the development of rural and urban territories and for the well-being of their inhabitants must be recognised. Positive environmental amenities (landscape, well-being, climate regulation, biodiversity, etc.) must be enhanced through financial mechanisms implemented at European and national level. In addition, it is important to develop reciprocity and solidarity between urban and rural areas, particularly on the issue of natural resource management (such as water for example), but also in terms of mobility, and to promote the attractiveness of these territories (support for the development of local tourism or relocatable services, support for the installation of new activities, etc.).

1.1.6. FACILITIES AND SERVICES

A special effort must be made to allow equitable access across all rural areas to quality services and equipment. The process of gradual disappearance of local public services must be stopped and, where possible, reversed. Initiatives aimed at alleviating these closures and strengthening local public services must be promoted, and European, national or regional funding adapted to them be dedicated to them (public service houses, France services territories, delegation of public services to local shops, rural multiservice shops, etc.). The opening up of isolated territories must continue to promote this access to services.

Without replacing the essential human presence, the development of digital technology with the dematerialisation of public services and the generalisation of Open Data can also promote access to certain essential services, including health, but also to cultural and commercial services for the vast majority of users, especially in isolated areas.

1.1.7. GOVERNANCE

To support the transition of rural territories imposed by current and future developments, new tools and modes of governance must be developed and implemented at local and regional levels.

The first step is to simplify administrative complexity in institutions governing rural areas, and to improve coordination between European, national and regional support structures and tools.

Any regional strategy in favour of rural areas should first and foremost promote greater coherence between the various programs and tools that can be mobilised, in order to become more effective and efficient.

Territorial approaches at the level of institutionalised groups of municipalities should be based on updated territorial diagnoses, ensuring that the existing perimeters and meshes (regional natural park, Local Action Group, etc.) are inclusive and cover interstitial areas. The development of small rural centralities should also make it possible to strengthen the territorial network, in addition to the larger projects carried by the large inter-municipal authorities.

Citizen involvement must also be strengthened to move from simple involvement to the co-construction of public policies for a renewed territorial approach. Thus, the development, implementation and monitoring of projects should be inclusive to all stakeholders, in order to promote proposals from the territories themselves. Better access to digital technology is also a vector of social and territorial innovation, notably through the development of "smart villages".

It is also important that administrative and financial procedures, in particular concerning European projects, including within the framework of the ERDF and the EAFRD, are simplified. The financing tools must be adapted or new tools created to allow a change of scale or the spin-off of projects, to finance more fully the operation, but also the animation, the training and the actions of information and pedagogy. Specific financing tools must be developed for hybrid projects that take into account and enhance the social utility of these projects. It is also important to find financial tools to take on the pre-financing of projects.

Finally, to promote the emergence of these projects and allow their implementation and monitoring, it is essential to provide and pool support in terms of territorial engineering intended for municipalities, institutionalised groups of municipalities etc., but also other local actors (associative structures, citizens' groups, development agencies, etc.), with the assistance in particular of the National Agency for Territorial Cohesion.

1.2. Thematic priorities, objectives and measures identified

During the second workshop, 8 priorities were identified to achieve this desirable future in rural areas: access to housing, mobility, access to local services, access to digital technology, adaptation to climate change, the economy and employment, the agricultural and food sector and finally the tourism sector. For each of these priorities, 2 objectives have been identified, as well as transitional measures, tools to be mobilised, the actors concerned or constraints to be overcome. We present here the first possible answers which, given the number of subjects raised, should be completed and refined.

In addition, we are devoting a specific part to the issue of governance, which was the subject of an additional videoconference on October 6th. It is a transversal and central subject for the sustainable and effective implementation of the various transition measures.

1.2.1. ACCESS TO HOUSING IN RURAL AREAS

This is a central element in terms of attractiveness for rural areas. Main issues about access to housing are:

- The rise in the price of land, due to the increase in demand for primary housing but also for second home.
- Competition between the different housing demands (natives, new arrivals in primary residence and secondary residents).
- The search for social diversity in rural areas.

- The reception capacity of rural areas in a constrained context, due to the limitation of the urban sprawling on agricultural land and natural spaces (Climate and resilience law).
- The need to adapt existing housing, sometimes built several decades ago (see the existence of thermal strainers, especially in mountain areas).

To remedy this, **the identified transition measures** are as follows:

Ensure a mix of housing in rural areas

- Fight against vacant housing, including by appropriating it (law on the right to housing enforceable). However, it is sometimes difficult to measure the number of visitors / vacancies in secondary houses.
- Develop intergenerational co-rental housing projects (cf. LEADER Pays project, in Arles).
- Develop citizen participatory housing.
- Attract new social operators (associations) who offer innovative housing projects.
- Take into account the typology of housing to be considered, in particular to meet a demand for small housing.
- Strengthen and simplify access to information on aid for home renovation and ecological conversion for individuals (Maisons France Service, ANCT).

It should be noted that the objective of zero net artificialisation by 2040, which some integrated local urban planning should anticipate, is a growing constraint to be taken into account for the construction of new housing.

Rehabilitate old housing and adapt existing housing

- Thermic and energy renovation: many public subsidies can be mobilised for municipalities and individuals, but application files are often complex to manage.
- Improve the brightness of housing and provide private outdoor spaces.
- Work with innovative architects on an architectural revolution in rural areas to integrate and transmit know-how for a living architectural heritage.

It should be noted that measures are provided for in the Rural Agenda and in the region's Climate Plan.

1.2.2. MOBILITY IN RURAL AREAS

Mobility is the other central subject for the attractiveness of rural areas because it allows access to employment and essential services. For the inhabitants of rural areas, mobility is ensured by the private car which depends on fossil fuels and emits GHGs. Yet today there are very few alternative mobility solutions.

Two main objectives have been identified here:

- Develop alternative modes of transport to the car and to "self-reliance" that are adapted to rural areas.
- Improve the territorial network and the coordination between the different territories (institutionalised groups of municipalities).

The avenues of transition measures identified and discussed during the second workshop are as follows:

- Development of solidarity mobility for people looking for work, the elderly, the sick or living with a disability who find it difficult to access services that are essential.
- Development of collective initiatives supported or not by the municipalities: carpooling, transport on demand at the level of living areas or a valley.

- Development of multimodal transport platforms in small and medium-sized rural centralities.
- Development of rural mobility plans and cycling schemes, when the terrain makes them possible and accessible.
- Development of charging stations for electric cars with a tight mesh of the territory
- Less transport, when possible, through teleworking, coworking, videoconferences, teleadmin, and telemedicine, to bring together places of life, work and residence (relocation of production).
- Support for small daily rail lines and maintenance of rural stations.
- Rethink the school transport system in rural areas and possibly open it up to other audiences (more local governance) to ensure the public service.
- Mobilisation of public funds dedicated to available mobility.

1.2.3. ACCESS TO LOCAL SERVICES

The economic and social vitality and the attractiveness of rural areas depends on access to local services at the level of living areas. Three types of services in particular are mentioned: primary schools, general practitioners, and local services/shops (café, bakery, banking annexes, etc.), which are also places of conviviality.

However, public services are declining in rural areas, including the closure of classes and/or schools, massive retirement of general practitioners who are difficult to replace, and the closure of local shops.

Two main objectives have been retained here:

- Maintain basic services in rural areas (school, doctor, etc.);
- Support and attract new local services.

The avenues of transition measures identified and discussed during the second workshop are as follows:

Maintain basic services in rural areas (school, doctor, etc.)

- Stabilise the small rural centralities, by preserving the schools to keep the basins of life
- Generalise the rurality conventions by supporting them on regional educational projects and apply them regionally to the rurality conventions within the "education" components of the governmental recovery and ecological transition contracts (CRTE). This is about proposing solutions adapted to the demographic and geographic challenges of each territory, based on a diagnosis shared by local actors.
- Continue the development of nursing homes.
- Develop the solidarity mobility offer for the transport of elderly and sick people (see mobility section).
- Make rural areas more attractive to encourage the installation, in particular of general practitioners (wages, local services including schools, evolution of the rural medicine model to take into account the quality of life of new settlers and their families, etc.).
- Develop telemedicine, but in addition to the installation of doctors.
- Sustain and develop existing systems such as professional and territorial health communities, public service engagement contracts, regional general medicine practitioners, installation assistance, tax exemptions or the maintenance of local hospital structures.
- Recruit salaried doctors assigned to the least endowed areas.

Support and attract new local services

- Concerning public services, stop their closure and / or development of *Maison France services*.
- Public service delegations to shops, cafes, etc., which are remunerated.
- Carrying out a diagnosis of the economy and jobs in the territory, in particular to imagine and identify the activities and services of tomorrow (cf. CRTE).
- Development of cooperative societies of collective interest (SCIC) in which the municipality can participate to meet collective needs.
- Use of LEADER support for the development of local shops and services.
- Mobilisation of "Living Villages" which is a rural and solidarity land company, which buys, renovates and rents premises to set up activities that have a positive impact on their territory and its inhabitants (<https://villagesvivants.com/>).
- Active France and France Network and Initiative mobilisation to support and finance entrepreneurs.

1.2.4. DIGITAL ACCESS IN RURAL AREAS

Access to digital technology has become essential for the development and attractiveness of rural areas, and more particularly concerns:

- Development of economic activity and improvement of competitiveness.
- The development of teleworking which promotes the installation of new inhabitants.
- Access to many remote services (commercial or public: health, online public services, etc.).

But there is a digital divide:

- Existence of blackspots and poor connection quality in isolated areas.
- Digital inclusion issues.

The two objectives retained here are:

- Develop a digital offer adapted to different rural territories (4G / 5G / fiber, etc.).
- Reduce the digital divide and fight against digital illiteracy.

The avenues of transition measures identified and discussed during the second workshop are as follows:

Develop a digital offer adapted to different rural territories (4G / 5G / fiber, etc.)

- The Provence Alpes-Côte d'Azur region has already defined a common digital regional development strategy in May 2018, which plans to cover the entire territory in 2050 for very high-speed broadband and to become a Smart region.

Reduce the digital divide and fight against digital illiteracy

- Development of a third place offering digital access for all (France service, *Bistrots*, projects supported by citizens, etc.)
- Transfer to other rural territories of the approach initiated by the Provence Alpes Côte d'Azur region as part of the Smart Rurality project, with the support of the Regional Rural Network and in collaboration with the Development Agency 04 and the Community of Communes Alpes Provence Verdon.
- Development of France Service spaces which offer one-stop shops to users of public services.
- Training of residents in the use of IT tools.

- Support for digital inclusion (Hub development for Digital Inclusion in Auvergne Rhône-Alpes in which ADRETS participates).
- Mobilisation of available public funding.
- Note that the ANCT also offers support to resolve the digital divide.

1.2.5. ADAPTATION TO THE EFFECTS OF CLIMATE CHANGE

The IPCC foresees for the Provence Alpes Côte d'Azur region an accentuation of the effects of climate change in the short and medium term, having a lasting impact on biodiversity, water resources, and forests, as well as the agricultural sector and tourism.

We also note:

- Awareness of the effects of climate change with the increase in natural disasters.
- Changes in practices are still slow and limited (cf. agricultural sector).

Two major topics were raised during the interviews:

- Water resources management (sobriety / quality).
- The fight against natural risks – in particular floods, droughts and fires.

This has **two main objectives**: better management of water resources; development of measures and aid to the agricultural and forestry sector to fight against natural risks (i.e., agri-environmental and climate measures (AECM), etc.).

Better manage water resources

- Imperative need for a territorial systemic approach: the scale is not the farm-holding but the watershed, the valley, or the specific territory.
- Promote sobriety in the use of water and therefore manage the sharing of water resources between upstream and downstream, between towns and countryside, and between different sectors of the economy, through solidarity and cooperation between territories from the same watershed.
- Develop agri-environmental measures and payments for ecosystem services in favour of better water management by the agricultural sector, including its quality (i.e., intermediate nitrate trap crops, reduction of phytosanitary products in drinking water catchment areas), and accompanying measures to adapt equipment favouring more water-efficiency, and water-efficient irrigation methods.
- Work on social acceptability to accept and implement the measures: scientific research interface/elected officials/civil society actors.
- Work on forecasts in terms of the impact of climate change on large basins (Verdon, Durance) according to downstream water demand.

Develop measures and support to the agricultural sector to fight against natural risks

- Develop support measures for the agricultural and forestry sectors to fight against natural risks (i.e., AECM, etc.).
- Promote solutions based on nature and ecosystem services in these support mechanisms.
- Take into account the positive amenities of the agricultural sector to aid the fight against natural risks on the basis of the natural risk map (including in ERDF programs).
- Develop aid for specific agricultural installations in these risk areas (reconquest of agricultural land).

- Establish a strong policy of reclaiming pastoral areas.
- Recognise the rural areas with high natural value in regional planning documents.
- Modify the (integrated) local urban planning to take better account natural disaster prevention.

1.2.6. THE AGRICULTURAL AND FOOD SECTOR

The agricultural sector faces many challenges:

- Renewal of generations.
- Land pressure and installation difficulties.
- Taking into account strong natural constraints and adaptation to climate change, including irrigation water management.
- Taking into account new societal expectations regarding respect for the environment and food supply.
- Social management of agricultural labour, including imported.

Two major issues were identified during the interviews:

- The difficulty of setting up new farmers in connection with land pressure.
- Support and reinforcement of good practices that containment seems to have reinforced (see short circuits).

The objectives adopted here are:

- Facilitate the installation of new farmers by controlling land for agricultural activity through spatial planning documents.
- Support and strengthen short supply chains and other good agricultural practices.

The avenues of transition measures identified and discussed during the second workshop are as follows:

Facilitate the installation of new farmers by controlling land for agricultural activity through spatial planning documents

- Stop the artificialisation of agricultural land by adopting and implementing the objective of zero net artificialisation (within spatial planning documents).
- Revalue, through agriculture, fallow land and afforestation with productive potential on the basis of a territorial diagnosis to assess the land supply and put into perspective the redevelopment of part of the lost agricultural areas (wasteland, forests, touristic area).
- Implement agricultural projects to protect and mobilise agricultural land, for example the "Protect and mobilise agricultural land" project in the *Alpilles Regional Natural Park*.
- Integrate installation and transmission projects within the framework of Territorial Food Programs (PAT) and support for sustainable agriculture.

Support and strengthen short supply chains and other good agricultural practices

- Develop and implement Territorial Food Programs (PAT) throughout the region at the level of communities of communes and urban metropolis.
- Promote the organisation of agricultural sectors to promote resilience during crises and promote better remuneration for farmers.

- Promote the development of short food supply chains projects (LEADER project, EAFRD support, support from chambers of agriculture, public funding, etc.).
- Reinforce the CAP support for organic production and for low pesticides farming systems.

1.2.7. THE TOURISM SECTOR

Tourism is a unifying sector for rural territories

- In terms of jobs.
- In terms of activity and wealth creation.
- In terms of the vitality and development of these territories

The sector is facing:

- The effects of climate change, in particular in alpine territories.
- To new societal expectations and new tourism demands.

While the sector as a whole has been particularly impacted by the health crisis, notably with a decrease in international visitors, rural tourism seems to be experiencing a revival by highlighting its local roots and its authenticity and by responding to new societal expectations, in particular by terms of well-being, a return to nature and respect for the environment, and new forms of tourism.

Two main objectives have been retained here:

- Develop and consolidate rural tourism that responds to climate challenges and new societal expectations.
- Build a new tourism model in mountain areas.

Develop and consolidate rural tourism that responds to climate challenges and new societal expectations

- Define rural tourism in connection with the new definition of 'rural' by INSEE, in order to characterise it and thus be able to promote it.
- Develop mixed tourism-local services schemes.
- Develop aid for agritourism like the Agritourism Pass set up in Occitania region.
- Promote the pooling and sharing of experiences between communities and massifs.
- Strengthen the special status of seasonal workers and multi-active workers to help improve the attractiveness of rural areas.
- Align the mobility system with tourist attractiveness and performance (cf. Tourism economy development plan).
- Develop for each territory a tourist office, taking into account the existing and future effects of climate change.

Building a new tourist model in mountain areas

- Develop a mountain tourism offer that takes into account the present and future effects of climate change.
- Ensure complementarity between winter (resort) and summer tourism.
- Work on the management of the housing supply and the upgrading of old housing (see previous point).

- Mobilise the Network of the Valleys areas, in terms of strategy development, financing and engineering.

The Tourism Economy Development Plan (Regional Tourism Development Plan 2017-2022) is the regional framework within which tourism strategies and projects should fit. It notably includes a chapter, "Adapting the mountain offer".

It should also be noted that the ANCT is developing a "*Mountains fit for the future*" plan which aims to build a tourism model that is both more diversified and more sustainable for mountain territories, in close collaboration with its main players, including local authorities.

1.3. Governance of the resilience of rural territories How to manage transitions?

The issue of "the governance of resilience in rural areas: how to manage transitions?" was the subject of an additional videoconference on October 6th. It is a cross-cutting and central topic for the sustainable and effective implementation of the various transitional measures mentioned above.

In terms of governance and management of rural areas in the Provence Alpes Côte d'Azur region, individual interviews revealed a certain number of observations which confirm the orientations of the first positioning document:

- The existence of a multiplicity of European, national and regional support structures and tools, which is difficult to grasp for local actors and project leaders, and which poses problems of coherence and coordination, while the network of territories is incomplete or overlaps.
- An increasing complexity of administrative tools and procedures, in particular for European funding and in particular LEADER funding (which moves this program away from its core target despite its recognised usefulness).
- Inadequate funding tools: funding duration too short for innovative projects requiring a long time; financing favouring investments to the detriment of operating expenses; pre-financing needs that are difficult to meet.
- A lack of project engineering (file preparation, financing, but also monitoring and animation) on the territory, particularly for small communities and project leaders.
- Too little involvement of citizens in the development and implementation of territorial strategies and the training needs of elected officials and potential project leaders concerning the issues, the tools that can be mobilised, and the possible funding.

During the videoconference organised on this subject, the objective of the discussions was to come up with concrete proposals in terms of steering transitions in rural areas by answering the following questions:

- What relevant scales of governance, what coordination?
- What kind of engineering, territorial contractualisation and animation?
- What policy instruments, funding, monitoring and evaluation tools?
- How to involve more citizens more effectively?

1.3.1. RELEVANT GOVERNANCE SCALES, WHAT COORDINATION?

The multiplicity of structures, strategies and support instruments, but also the vagueness of the action parameters and the lack of coordination make it difficult to understand the mechanisms in rural areas,

especially for small municipalities and the promoters of private and associative projects. A first proposal would be for the Provence Alpes Côte d'Azur region to create and distribute a mapping of these structures, their skills, their scope of intervention and the funding tools available. This would make it possible to account for the existing governance network of rural areas so that it is ultimately more inclusive and integrates interstitial zones.

Then it should be remembered that at the regional level, the regional spatial planning document (SRADDET) is the document which ensures the consistency and complementarity of the various strategies and instruments available, including national and European ones. The process of deepening the objective of strengthening an exemplary rural model could be an opportunity to discuss this necessary coordination. At the national level, it is the Rural Agenda which is the relevant framework, and which constitutes the action plan in favour of rural territories. Finally, the recovery and ecological transition contract (CRTE) is the tool for coordinating and structuring public policies in rural areas.

For better coordination, and because there is not one rurality but multiple ruralities, it is necessary to favour territorial approaches, based on territorial diagnoses. As one of the members of the platform indicates, for the Pays d'Arles, such diagnoses already exist in the spatial planning document, for example, which is included in the CRTE. These CRTEs, which replace the rurality contracts, will be signed between the national government and the sub-regional entity (PETR, community of communes or urban metropolis), lasting 6 years.

The CRTE's ambition is to be based on a territorial project developed collectively on the basis of a territorial diagnosis. Another member of the platform thus underlines that governance must take place at the level of a project area because it allows transversality.

1.3.2. WHAT POLICY INSTRUMENTS, FINANCING, MONITORING AND EVALUATION TOOLS?

The observation is unanimous among the members of the SHERPA MAP: administrative and financial procedures, especially for European projects, have become more complex at all levels (Europe, France, Region).

Projects are becoming more and more cumbersome, and pre-financing needs difficult to bear for small municipalities and project leaders, which favour the largest municipalities and organised groups of municipalities, already the best endowed and who generally know the networks and decision-making levers best. In the Provence Alpes Côte d'Azur region, the envelope for LEADER projects for 2021-2027 will decrease slightly, but there will be new EAFRD funding available for rural areas and a new envelope of €20 million is devoted to the Rural ERDF (but recommending amounts greater than €100,000 in the Rural ERDF).

In addition to the need to building territorial projects based on territorial diagnostics (see previous point), so that the projects respond to the challenges of these territories, several proposals were raised by the members of the platform on this subject.

First of all, in order to meet the ambition set out in its long-term vision for rural areas, it is essential for the European Commission to set minimum percentages of the ERDF and EAFRD budgets dedicated to rural development, in order to avoid funding being mainly directed towards aid to the agricultural sector.

With regard to financing, we can question the desire expressed in the framework of the rural ERDF for projects of a minimum amount of € 100 000 which aim at structuring investments, but exclude a large part of the targets of rural development projects: in particular small municipalities and private and associative project leaders. This minimum amount makes it all the more necessary to maintain and strengthen the LEADER program, which makes it possible to promote innovative and sustainable projects, meeting the expectations of the territories and financial amounts that are manageable and bearable by project leaders. By relying on the facilitation of LAGs, the LEADER system makes it possible to identify the needs of local actors in these territories and thus collectively select coherent projects that meet these expectations.

However, the increasingly complex administrative and financial procedures, including for cooperation funding and high management costs, increasingly distance this system from the rural actors who need it most. It is therefore urgent that the European Commission, the State, and the Region, work in conjunction with project leaders to simplify these procedures. For LEADER or other initiatives, it is also a question of broadening funding to give a more important place to experimentation and innovation (including continuity), as well as allowing the change of scale or spin-off of projects that have shown their relevance, in order to move from "small innovative projects" to structuring projects. It is also important to provide, in LEADER projects, for larger lines of funding for operation, and for facilitation, training and information and educational actions. Specific financing tools should also be developed for hybrid projects that take into account and enhance the social utility of these projects.

Animation through the LAGs is a major added value of the LEADER system, it is essential that this function is reinforced (in terms of budget and skills) in order to ensure the continuity of the system on the territory and the quality of the service offered, but also that the whole of the regional territory be covered.

The pre-financing of projects whose payment terms are getting longer and longer is a major issue, especially for small municipalities and those with private and associative projects. Several avenues can be explored: on the one hand, reducing payment terms, on the other hand, benefiting from a project pre-financing. Pre-financing or bridging loans by a private bank could also be considered, with a guarantee from the Region or the State. ACIDI or the France Active network can be avenues for pre-financing.

In addition, the *Pays d'Arles* suggested the possibility of public-private governance of European projects and within the framework of the possibility of a transfer by the Region of the management of part of the European funds.

1.3.3. WHAT ENGINEERING, TERRITORIAL CONTRACTING AND ANIMATION?

There is a need for engineering and project management technical assistance (monitoring of call for proposals, setting up of financial engineering programs, monitoring-evaluation, etc.). This technical assistance is essential in particular for the smallest municipalities, but also for small project leaders (associative structures, citizens' groups, etc.), should be able to mobilise all the skills useful for setting up and monitoring projects.

This territorial engineering must be pooled. Specific funding should be provided to promote this support, either at the level of the projects themselves (dedicated budget lines), or at the level of the ANCT. In the region, such territorial engineering exists in particular in the Department of Hautes Alpes (Territorial Engineering IT05) and in the Department of Alpes de Hautes Provence (Development Agency IT04) and more specific engineering concerning, for example, tourism.

1.3.4. HOW TO MORE AND BETTER INVOLVE CITIZENS?

Citizen involvement must also be strengthened to move from simple involvement to the co-construction of public policies for a renewed territorial approach. Thus, the development, implementation and monitoring of projects must be inclusive and involve all stakeholders, in order to promote proposals from the territories themselves.

However, today the associative commitment on which the citizen mobilisation was based is declining. The abstention rate, even if it is lower than in the city, is also increasing and the legitimacy of elected officials decreases. Development councils (CD) exist in the institutionalised groups of municipalities are insufficient: institutionalised, consultative and sometimes little listened to, they often bring together the same citizens and do not include any silent majorities. In the most isolated municipalities, it is often difficult to mobilise citizens because of commuting and scarce time available. In some areas, newcomers, including residents of

secondary homes, are sometimes more involved than the older inhabitants. In addition, establishing trust relationships to explain and co-construct public policies and joint projects takes time.

If the CDs must be better taken into account and the voices of citizens listened to, beyond institutionalised agoras we are witnessing the emergence of new forms of citizen mobilisation: citizens' councils, eco-delegates, the movement of cities in transition, new CAP network... on which we can rely. We can bring together these citizens who want to act through membership of common charters on unifying projects (see for example the creation of territorial food projects).

In addition, the debate at the municipal level is essential because the mayor is the representative at the level of the communities of communes, the regional natural parks, etc. An external animation effort is required and must lead the support of citizen action in concrete engagements (cf. participatory projects). Information and communication for civil society and citizen collectives is also a major issue, concerning both the challenges of rural areas and the public policies implemented at the different levels of decision-making. This is also the case for the training of citizens in the challenges of rural areas. The development of third places, places of exchange and creative information, in rural areas can, also support citizen mobilisation. Ad-hoc funding must be provided for this in the projects.

Better access to digital technology is also a vector of social and territorial innovation, notably through the development of "smart villages". It can promote a co-constructed approach between actors from various backgrounds, combining local resources and skills, and possibly mobilising digital tools to respond to current and future rural challenges on mobility, governance, citizenship, the environment, quality of life or the economy.

In this context, at the level of the living areas of institutionalised groups of municipalities, it is also a question of developing territorial approaches, based on territorial diagnosis, ensuring that the existing network (regional natural park, Local Action Group, etc.) is inclusive and integrates interstitial zones. The development of small rural centralities should make it possible to strengthen the territorial network, in addition to the larger projects carried by the large inter-municipal authorities.

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Bibliography

A highly urbanised region and growing artificialisation of land

- INSEE, Une consommation foncière deux fois plus rapide que l'évolution démographique, INSEE Analyses, Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur, n°40 Novembre 2016
- INSEE, Portrait de la région Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur, INSEE Etudes, Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur, Juillet 2012
- INSEE, Atlas régional, Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur parmi les nouvelles régions françaises, INSEE Dossier, Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur, n°4 Juin, 2016
- Réseau rural, reseaurural.maregionsud.fr/chantiers/projet-alimentaire-territorial/enjeux-agricoles/reseaurural.maregionsud.fr/chantiers/projet-alimentaire-territorial/enjeux-agricoles/

Demographic slowdown and aging of the population

- INSEE, Qui détient les résidences secondaires ? Six profils territoriaux, INSEE Analyses Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur, 16 février 2021
- INSEE, Faible croissance démographiques dans les communes densément peuplées, INSEE Flash, Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur, n°60, Décembre 2019
- INSEE, Populations légales Populations légales : Faible croissance démographique dans les communes densément peuplées, INSEE Flash, Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur, n°60 Décembre 2019
- INSEE, Les jeunes de Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur : quand la vie adulte se fait attendre, INSEE Analyse, Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur, n°76, Octobre 2019
- INSEE, Vieillesse de la population, perte d'autonomie et dépendance à l'horizon 2030 en Vaucluse, INSEE Dossier, Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur, n°10, Octobre 2019
- INSEE La progression démographique ralentit dans les couronnes périurbaines, INSEE Flash, Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur, n°48, Janvier 2019
- INSEE, Populations légales : 5 021 928 habitants en Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur au 1 er janvier 2016, INSEE Flash, Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur, n°47, Décembre 2018
- INSEE, Perte d'autonomie des seniors à domicile : plus fréquente en Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur, INSEE Flash, Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur, n°41, Juin 2018
- Région Sud, Vieillesse de la population et territoire en Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur: quelles interactions ?, Connaissances du territoire, janvier 2018
- DREAL Provence Alpes Côte d'Azur, les dynamiques démographiques, Fiche 1.1 , Atlas régional de l'habitat, 2018

Management of natural resources and climate change

- GREC-Sud, Les effets du changement climatique sur l'agriculture et la forêt en Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur, novembre 2016
- GREC-Sud, Climat et changement climatique en région Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur, mai 2016
- GREC-Sud, Provence Alpes Côte d'Azur, une région face au changement climatique, novembre 2015
- GREC-Sud, Provence Alpes Côte d'Azur, une région face au changement climatique, juin 2015
- <http://www.meteofrance.fr/climat-passe-et-futur/climathd>
- INSEE, Atlas régional Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur parmi les nouvelles régions françaises, INSEE Dossier Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur, n°4 juin 2016

Main economic trends in the region

- Frezel J, Lazzeri Y, Merle V, Les Systèmes alimentaires territorialisés en Méditerranée, Journal Resolis 12, juillet 2016
- <http://draaf.paca.agriculture.gouv.fr/Emploi,138>
- <http://draaf.paca.agriculture.gouv.fr/Les-installations-d-exploitants>
- <http://draaf.paca.agriculture.gouv.fr/Les-installations-d-exploitants>
- <https://lest.fr/fr/articles/2020/04/covid-19-et-main-doeuvre-etrangere-deux-articles-avec-frederic-decosse>
- <https://reseau rural.maregionsud.fr/chantiers/projet-alimentaire-territorial/enjeux-agricoles/> : ONAB, L'agriculture biologique en Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur, Edition 2019
- <https://reseau rural.maregionsud.fr/chantiers/projet-alimentaire-territorial/>
- INSEE, Atlas Régional, Provence Alpes Côte 'Azur parmi les nouvelles régions françaises, INSEE Dossier n°4, juin 2016
- INSEE, L'économie du tourisme en Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur, INSEE Dossier Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur, n°8, juin 2018

- L'agriculture, l'agro-alimentaire et la forêt dans la région Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur, Agreste ; Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur, Décembre 2019
- ZAP Tourisme, Suivi de l'activité touristique 2018/19
- Plan de croissance de développement de l'économie touristique, Plan de croissance de l'économie touristique, Schéma Régional de Développement Touristique 2017-2022, Région Sud
- Ministère de l'agriculture et de l'alimentation, Redévelopper les espaces agricoles en région Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur - Analyse n°167, 12 juillet 2021

Access to services

- INSEE, Une région bien équipée mais des populations encore isolées, INSEE Etudes Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur, n° 8, juin 2011
- INSEE, Equipement et services, Bonne accessibilité dans les communes peu denses grâce au tourisme, INSEE Flash n° 22, janvier 2016
- INSEE, Service à la population : des points d'accès de plus en plus nombreux, INSEE Flash, n°43, septembre 2019

Social Cohesion and living environment

- INSEE, Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur, le cadre de vie, moteur des déménagements, INSEE Analyses, n°36, octobre 2016
- INSEE, Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur, des territoires ruraux peu peuplés mais dynamiques, INSEE Analyses, n°22 septembre 2015

Digitisation

- Région Provence Alpes-Côte d'Azur, Stratégie commune d'aménagement numérique du territoire, mai 2018
- ADRETS, Smart Village, janvier 2020
- <https://agence-cohesion-territoires.gouv.fr/fiches-actions-numerique-dans-les-crte-544>

General documents

- CESE, L'économie de proximité : une réponse aux défis majeurs de la société française, 2010
- Fiori S & Magnaghi A, « Les territoires du commun. Entretien avec Alberto Magnaghi », Métropolitiques, 10 mai 2018. URL : <http://www.metropolitiques.eu/Les-territoiresdu-commun.html>.
- OCDE, Synthèse sur le changement d'échelle et l'impact des entreprises sociales, 2016
- Le schéma régional d'aménagement, de développement durable et d'égalité des territoires (SRADDET), Région Sud, Octobre 2019
- Programme Opérationnel FEDER-FSE, Provence Alpes Côte d'Azur 2014-2020
- <https://www.reseaurural.fr/le-fonds-europeen-agricole-pour-le-developpement-rural-en-france/les-20-fiches-mesures-du-feader>
- <https://reseaurural.maregionsud.fr/chantiers/projet-alimentaire-territorial/le-reseau-des-pat-en-region-sud/>
- Le guide du Plan de relance à destination des maires
<https://www.bouches-du-rhone.gouv.fr/content/download/42085/239081/file/Guide%20France%20Relance%20%C3%A0%20destination%20des%20maires.pdf>
- Les cartes des CRTE
<https://agence-cohesion-territoires.gouv.fr/les-cartes-433>
- Appel à projets Plan de relance

<https://www.economie.gouv.fr/plan-de-relance/appels-projets#>

Some reference sites

- <https://www.reseaurural.fr>
- <https://pays-arles.org/>
- <https://paysgrandbrianconnais.fr/detail/le-pole-dequilibre-territorial-et-rural-1>
- <https://agence-cohesion-territoires.gouv.fr/>
- <https://www.observatoire-des-territoires.gouv.fr/>
- <http://www.sirsepaca.org/#c=home>
- <https://rural-interfaces.eu/>
- <https://rural-interfaces.eu/newsletter/>

CRTEs in the Provence Alpes Côte d'Azur region

Bouches-du-Rhône

- <https://cartotheque.anct.gouv.fr/media/record/eyJpIjoiZGVmYXVsdCIsm0iOm51bGwsImQiOjEsInIiOjM5Njd9/>

Alpes de Hautes Provence

- <https://cartotheque.anct.gouv.fr/media/record/eyJpIjoiZGVmYXVsdCIsm0iOm51bGwsImQiOjEsInIiOjM5NjR9/>

Alpes Maritimes

- <https://cartotheque.anct.gouv.fr/media/record/eyJpIjoiZGVmYXVsdCIsm0iOm51bGwsImQiOjEsInIiOjM5NjZ9/>

Hautes Alpes

- <https://cartotheque.anct.gouv.fr/media/record/eyJpIjoiZGVmYXVsdCIsm0iOm51bGwsImQiOjEsInIiOjM5NjV9/>

Var

- <https://cartotheque.anct.gouv.fr/media/record/eyJpIjoiZGVmYXVsdCIsm0iOm51bGwsImQiOjEsInIiOjM5Njh9/>

Vaucluse

- <https://cartotheque.anct.gouv.fr/media/record/eyJpIjoiZGVmYXVsdCIsm0iOm51bGwsImQiOjEsInIiOjM5Njl9/>

Annex 1. Methodology used by the Platform

Composition of the Multi-Actor Platform

During this second phase, the composition of the platform has undergone several adaptations:

- External resource persons are now an integral part of the platform. This concerns, in particular, representatives of INSEE, GREC, the Regional Chamber of Agriculture and DRAAF, agents from the South Region as well as from the Hautes Alpes Department.
- New representatives of public decision-makers have also been integrated: in particular two rural mayors, one of whom is also a Regional Councillor, but also representatives of INSEE, DRAAF, the Regional Chamber of Agriculture and the
- In this complicated health context, it was more difficult to involve researchers, especially during the workshops.

Progress of the second phase

This second phase took place in several stages:

- A first workshop introducing the JRC scenarios on rural areas by 2040 was held on July 1, semi-face-to-face.

The scenarios as well as the SHERPA working document concerning the foresight exercise were translated and distributed to members of the platform. An introductory note and a PowerPoint presentation were also prepared to facilitate this workshop.

At the end of this workshop, a report was used as a basis for the individual interviews and the second workshop.

- Prior to the second workshop, around fifteen individual interviews were conducted from September 2-10, in order to re-specify to which scenario the rural territories of the Provence Alpes Côte d'Azur region correspond, which scenario to target, identify the main priorities to achieve "this desirable future", and specify some concrete objectives to be achieved.
- Based on the discussions of the first workshop and individual interviews, a second workshop was held semi-face-to-face on September 22. The aim was to present and discuss salient issues in terms of the transition of rural territories in the Provence Alpes Côte d'Azur region, which emerged during individual interviews, in order to arrive at a limited number of common or specific priorities, identify rural areas in the region, and define one or more achievable objectives to achieve our desirable future. An introductory note and a PowerPoint presentation have been prepared to facilitate this workshop.
- As the second workshop did not address the issue of governance, a videoconference was organised on October 6 on this subject.
- The draft of this second position paper of the Provence Alpes Côte d'Azur Region Platform was distributed to members of the platform on October 26 for review, amendment and finalisation.

Assessment of the scenarios and the method used

If the scenarios provide an interesting and structuring methodological contribution, the scenarios and the new methodology proposed have somewhat disrupted the work undertaken during the first phase. In Provence Alpes Côte d'Azur, the first phase had in fact already made it possible to identify the main issues facing rural areas. The scenarios having been little discussed upstream, it was difficult to assimilate and project into them.

Moreover, these scenarios were the subject of numerous reservations on the part of the members of the platform:

- The scenarios make too little reference to climate change and take little account of climatic trajectories, although these are major elements in terms of the transition of rural areas by 2040. The period 2020-40 is nevertheless a decisive period for limiting the effects of climate change (see in particular the drastic reduction in GHGs that is necessary).
- The place of natural areas is also little discussed in the scenarios, and the management of natural areas is a major issue for the South Region.
- The scenarios defend an ideological bias concerning the place of Europe in the development of public policies (top-down approach) and economic recovery based on growth, without any mention of the sharing of wealth. No downturn scenario is proposed.
- The scenarios give either very or too little importance place to technology, in particular in terms of governance, but also in the fight against climate change.
- Rural territories are never defined positively and as autonomous territories.
- The scenarios underline the attractiveness of rural territories that the development of teleworking, through the development of digital infrastructures would induce, but give little mention of who this attractiveness would concern, while making them selective territories.
- International issues and their impacts are approached too succinctly and should be developed, particularly with regard to the CAP.
- Concerning governance, the scenarios present at best a consultation process but no real inclusive co-decision process.
- The governance criterion, unlike the demographic criterion, is not very quantifiable. It would have been more effective to use an economic criterion, for example, to classify rural territories.

The proposed method, not having been co-constructed or proposed upstream to the platforms, was somewhat applied to the work already started during the first phase, and therefore was difficult to assimilate. Given the number of subjects addressed by the platform, it was difficult to fully unfold the method and perform the overhead projection. As indicated in the method presentation document, it would take more time to roll out this method in its entirety and two workshops, even with individual interviews is a bit too short.

Other difficulties or limitations encountered

- The health crisis, even if the conditions are easing, complicated the organisation of the work,
- As has been mentioned several times during cluster meetings, and with all of the SHERPA platforms, the use of English for all of the consortium's documents, in particular the scenarios, is a major constraint for the facilitation. But above all, it makes exchanges between platforms difficult for non-English speakers.

Ownership of results

In 2020, the SHERPA Platform for the Provence Alpes Côte d'Azur region has chosen the theme of the Long-term Vision for Rural Areas (LTVRA) to take a step back on the future challenges to be met in rural areas and for communities.

The results of the work of the SHERPA platform in the South region (Position paper, October 2020) were presented during the Regional Rural Network Forum, as well as in the working group of the European Network for Rural Development (ENRD) on the Long-term Vision for Rural Areas and have been very well received. They showed the usefulness of such a space for multi-stakeholder dialogue to better understand and take into account the diversity and richness of the region's rural territories. They have also helped to fuel the debate on rurality in the South region in the context of the development and implementation of

future EAFRD and ERDF / ESF. The Regional Council thus used the platform's first position paper to draft and vote for a special report on regional rural areas in December 2020: "Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur, a Region turned towards rurality". In addition, we are associated with the current work of INSEE on rurality and the results of this second phase will contribute to the discussions led by the Southern Region in the context of the programming and implementation of the EAFRD and ERDF instruments/FSE for the period 2021-2027 and also within the framework of the modification of the SRADDET.

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